

Parking Lots Management and Visualization in the Smart City - Digital Twin context

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Abstract—In recent years, extensive research has been conducted to develop traffic surveillance and monitoring applications using advanced technologies in a Smart-City context. One of the fundamental challenges in an urban city scenario is developing an efficient yet affordable parking lot management system. Such systems play a crucial role in providing the necessary data to local municipalities to make informed decisions to better manage the traffic flow while saving valuable resources and time. In this paper, we propose a novel end-to-end system architecture for a real-time video-based parking management system that can be easily scaled and enforced in a Smart-City context. Using state-of-the-art object detection and tracking methods combined with novel Static Object Detection techniques, we demonstrate a localized strategy for identifying potential parking spaces. A separate parking occupancy classification pipeline is discussed which provides fast and accurate availability status of these parking spaces. Furthermore, a 3D digital-twin application to monitor and visualize the parking spaces is demonstrated. Our experiments in a real-world scenario demonstrate the significant potential of our proposed architecture to easily scale to a given city with minimal manual efforts and lower implementation costs.

Index Terms—Deep Learning, Classification, Digital Twin, Smart City, Parking Detection, 5G network

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper proposes an efficient and sustainable vision-based Parking Space Detector (PSD) within a Smart-City context. Our Parking Space Detector (hereafter referred to as PSD) has been developed with consideration of factors such as ease of data accessibility, data anonymization, and scalable real-time connectivity, in order to offer a more comprehensive and effective Smart-City application package. Typically, parking detection systems resort to infrastructure-based methods which utilize sensors deployed with a predefined map of the parking areas. Although these systems work efficiently, their major disadvantage is that they require the installation of additional hardware according to the design of the parking areas. When compared to traditional parking systems, a single camera sensor can cover a large area of parking spaces, lowering the cost per parking space.

In this paper, we propose a vision-based Parking Space Detection (PSD) system architecture to detect parking spaces as well as their occupancy in real time in a convenient, efficient, and reliable way. We use these metrics to define the end performance goal of our proposed architecture. Convenience is the ease of deploying the architecture with minimal

manual efforts while providing options to customize its system components to generalize for a given environment; efficiency is about detecting space and achieving occupancy status in real time; reliability is about the consistent performance of individual system components in a given real-world scenario. Considering recent advances in artificial intelligence and computer vision, PSD utilizes a high-performance multi-object detector, a custom Static Object Detection (SOD) method, and an image classifier fine-tuned on a newer parking dataset. PSD is designed in such a way that, on the server side, there is a less computational load for determining the occupancy status of these parking spaces. The outcome of these processes results in a real time stream of data providing geo-location of all the potential parking spaces in the given scene, along with their current occupancy status. Information gathered about parking spots is then conveniently displayed within a custom-built 3D visualization application that provides real-time updates on these parking spaces. The transmission of data between the parking detection stage on the server and the 3D visualizer consumer application is handled by high-bandwidth Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) provided by an ongoing EU (European Union) project *5GMETA*. This ensures that the data is transmitted quickly and reliably, allowing the visualizer to provide accurate and up-to-date information to the user.

Initially, the system was tested on prerecorded video feeds from traffic surveillance cameras placed within Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA) which is a 2 square km urban city area instrumented with sensors and actuators. We then deployed the system on the local municipality server to test it using the live video feed from these cameras. These real-world tests demonstrate the ease of deploying the proposed architecture for a given traffic surveillance system and its ability to deliver optimal performance in challenging parking scenarios. This highlights the potential of the system as a Smart-City application.

The contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose an end-to-end system architecture utilizing computer vision and AI technologies to solve parking space detection challenges, which can be easily incorporated and scaled onto existing traffic surveillance systems.
- A novel vision-based parking detection strategy is provided which does not rely on prior knowledge of the park-

ing space layout, thus eliminating the need for additional manual pre-processing of data and hardware installations.

- A scalable and customizable end-to-end architecture is implemented by combining a state-of-the-art multi-object detector (Yolov5 + DeepSORT), a custom Static Object Detection method, and an image classifier trained on several parking datasets (PKLot, CNR-Park).
- A novel 3D visualizer application has been implemented to show the parking occupancy in real time, thus creating a digital twin of the smart city and improving the interaction between the city’s infrastructure and the road users.
- To demonstrate the ease of accessibility, security, and scalable real-time connectivity of data, an end-to-end data transmission pipeline is implemented and tested using high-bandwidth edge infrastructure provided by *5GMETA*.

II. RELATED WORK

Current parking detection methods can be broadly categorized into sensor-based [1]–[4] and computer vision based systems [5]–[8]. Traditional sensor-based systems are deployed at the entry and exit of small indoor and outdoor parking lots, thus keeping track of incoming and outgoing vehicles to determine the availability of parking spaces. Sensor-based systems like [9] rely on using ultrasonic or radar sensors which are installed in parking spaces to keep the track of occupancy of the parking areas. This information is then relayed to display panels, which guide the drivers to the available parking locations. However, in large parking spaces, the cost of covering many spots becomes significant. Also, installing sensor-based systems is not a practical solution for most outdoor parking scenarios and cannot be easily scaled in large urban areas. There has been considerable research on crowdsensing techniques [10], using drones or cars fitted with ultrasonic or camera sensors to gain insight into parking space information.

On the contrary, computer vision-based methods have been proven beneficial in most of the practical real-world scenarios, since camera sensors can cover a large area or parking lot and can be easily managed and installed in a given parking environment. Huang and Wang [5] showed that image-based parking detection can be categorized into space-driven and vehicle-driven methods. In the former technique, the focus is on observing a specific region of the scene for any variations. Initial studies began to solve parking detection challenges using simple features like color vectors to formulate it as a classification problem [8]. Training examples with these manually selected feature sets were then used to identify vehicle characteristics using hue histograms and support vector machines (SVM). Wu et al. [11] proposed defining color histogram across three spaces as a feature set in their SVM classifier to overcome occlusions. Recently, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) based architectures have also been proposed to classify the occupancy status of the given region [12]. Parking space-based methods provide higher accuracy on

the validation dataset, but they involve extensive manual effort in terms of data labeling and annotation for a given parking lot. Due to this nature, these methods are not easily scalable and require manual effort in calibrating the region of interest for every given camera. Also, in real-world scenarios, this process needs to be repeated every time the camera position changes due to any maintenance activity. Almeida and Oliveira [6] introduced a parking dataset PKLOT, consisting of 12417 images taken from three different views of two parking lots. Amato et al. [12] introduced a newer dataset with 150,000 images of 164 parking spaces in a lot, captured from over nine viewing angles. They further trained a classifier on this dataset to achieve over 98% accuracy. Acharya, D., Yan, W., and Khoshelham [13] built a classifier on the PKLOT dataset to achieve an accuracy of 96.6% but their evaluation dataset contained 30 parking spaces. Marek, M. [14] recently introduced a new dataset for image-based parking space occupancy classification that contains over 293 images but with over 11236 unique perspectives of the parking space. Using this dataset they implement a simple baseline classifier, achieving an accuracy of over 98% over unseen parking lots. As far as visualization systems are concerned, having connected vehicles be able to interact with a surrounding smart area poses new challenges for the system engineer. In the smart city era, in-vehicle information systems are designed to provide drivers with information about their surrounding environment, such as the presence of pedestrians, bicycles, and other vehicles, as well as information about road signs [15]. In this work, we extend over previous in-vehicle Human Machine Interfaces (HMI) to provide a 3D interactive graphic application that allows the user to seamlessly navigate within a city digital twin. Such an application will inform the user of the current state of the parking spaces detected by our proposed vision-based system.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Overview

An overview of the Parking Space Detection (PSD) system is shown below in Figure 1. The main system components can be broadly categorized into four stages: Parking Detection, Occupancy Classification, Data Processing & Transmission, and finally Visualization. The proposed system is designed considering a variety of possible centralized and edge computing traffic surveillance setups, thus providing wider flexibility in choosing alternative technologies for these components. As an input to the system, live RTSP video feed from cameras within the Smart City trial site is used. Parking detection and occupancy classification stages are deployed on a fog node of the local municipality server to maintain data privacy and security within their secured networks. In the parking detection stage, potential parking spaces are identified by utilizing state-of-the-art object detection and tracking algorithm (Yolov5 + DeepSORT). Live RTSP video feed is converted into object detections and vehicles are tracked in real time. Potential parking spaces are determined by the results of the object tracking algorithm. Here, we propose an online multi-object

tracking algorithm DeepSORT [16] considering its efficient performance on occlusion, lighting conditions, and identity switches.

A local database of all the identified parking spaces is then maintained on the fog node and is constantly checked for occupancy status using an image classifier. Parking detection and occupancy classification stages are implemented as two separate threads running on the fog node to efficiently utilize its computational power. Video frames received from traffic cameras are shared as a separate input to both of these processes which in turn makes the data sharing more efficient.

B. Parking Detection

Detecting parking lines marked on the tarmac from traffic cameras to identify a potential parking space, fails to achieve desired results from the perspective of a traffic surveillance camera. Usually, these parking lines are hindered by occlusion from parked cars and hence provide less amount of features to perform object detection with higher accuracy. Also, typically not all parking spaces are marked on the road, in such scenarios this strategy does not work. On the contrary, space-based methods as discussed before, rely on a classifier to determine whether the parking lot is occupied or not. In these implementations, although the classification accuracy is good, there is a lot of manual work involved in labeling available spaces manually according to the layout of the parking lot and this leads to a non-scalable approach for a Smart City application.

To achieve the best of both worlds, in this paper we use the vehicle-based method on received video frames from city surveillance cameras to identify parking locations, then we use a space-based method to obtain the occupancy status of that detected parking space.

In the past decade, there has been significant development and research in the area of object detection and tracking for surveillance and other industrial applications. Using these techniques it is possible to identify and track vehicles in real time and obtain precise boundaries of the objects. Apart from being accurate, vehicle detectors are also highly generalizable. After YOLO was proposed by R. Joseph et.al [17], the traditional detection philosophy of "proposing regions and then performing verification" over it was abandoned. Instead, utilizing a single neural network that divides images into regions to predict bounding boxes and probabilities of these regions simultaneously became a popular choice. Since then, there has been a series of improvements over the YOLO algorithm to further improve accuracy and detection speed. Ultralytics proposed YOLOv5 in 2020, making improvements YOLOv3, which is a lightweight detection network. In our implementation, we use a pre-trained YOLOv5 model on the MS-COCO dataset, which offers over 80 object categories including cars, motorcycles, trucks, bicycles, etc.

Since accurate object detection is the fundamental requirement for a reliable target tracker, in this work we utilize an implementation of YOLOv5 in PyTorch [18], [19]. This architecture of the YOLO family offers accurate target detections

and higher operational speed. YOLOv5 architecture consists of a CSP-Darknet53 backbone; the Neck part is SPPF which is an optimized version of Spatial Pyramid Pooling introduced in YOLOv3 originally [20] and CSP structures which speed up the transmission of feature information and feature fusion; Head part is from YOLOv3 which adopts bounding box loss function to achieve faster convergence effect.

For choosing a suitable tracking algorithm, they can be divided into traditional and deep learning algorithms. Traditional tracking algorithms like optical flow, mean shift, etc. offer poor performance under changes in lighting conditions, motion blur, and orientation of the target in the scene. Deep learning algorithms on the other hand perform faster accurate tracking with robustness. In real-world scenarios, multi-object tracking is more relevant and practical. Initially, the SORT algorithm was proposed by Bewley et al. [21] which inherently uses a combination of a Kalman Filter and Hungarian algorithm for tracking components with higher accuracy, but the performance was poor on occluded objects. DeepSORT later introduced by Wojke et al. [16] overcame this problem by implementing cascading association step using CNN-based object appearance features. We combine the object detections produced from YOLOv5 and pass them to the DeepSORT algorithm to keep track of all the objects being detected in the subsequent incoming frames.

To determine whether a region in the scene is a potential parking space, we first determine whether the tracked object is stationary or moving. A simple Static Object Detection method is implemented to achieve this. Within DeepSORT, the tracking scenarios are defined as an eight-dimensional state space $(u, v, \gamma, h, (x), (y), (\gamma), (h))$ wherein (u, v) define the bounding box center position, γ is the aspect ratio, h is the height and their respective velocities in image coordinates [16]. A recursive Kalman filtering is then used to predict and update the trajectory state. A subsequent number of frames are counted for each track k since the last successful measurement association a_k . The counter is reset to 0 whenever a track is associated with a measurement. Tracks that exceed a predefined maximum age are then discarded as the object is considered to have left the scene and new tracks are initiated for every new detection [16]. Using this, we set up another counter to check if a track k remains in the track list for a predefined minimum limit T_{sod} , this threshold is set high enough to isolate vehicles present in the scene for a longer duration (in our case parked vehicles). If a track is present in the scene for T_{sod} frames, we then check the associated velocities and image coordinates (u, v) for any variations in their measurements. To keep track of these variations in image coordinates, we check if the bounding box measurement deviations for the past T_{sod} frames are within the pre-defined threshold BB_{thres} . Tracks that have measurements under this threshold are then considered to be static.

All the detected static objects, in our case vehicles, are considered potential parking locations. Image coordinates of these objects including their unique identification number are stored locally, and further act as a database of parking spots

Fig. 1. System Architecture Overview

for a given camera.

C. Occupancy Classification

This stage is inspired by space-based parking detection methods wherein, generically, a specific region of the scene is manually recorded for observation. Then various computer vision methods from traditional classifiers [22] to recent deep learning techniques are used to classify whether the given space is occupied or not. Amato et al. [12] use a similar space-based approach discussed for smart cameras using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the classification of parking spaces, CNRPark-EXT dataset is also shared consisting of roughly 150000 labeled images of vacant and occupied parking spaces, built on a parking lot of 164 spaces. In our work, we utilize the Pytorch implementation of this providing us with comparable results with several parking datasets. But, we detect all the potential parking regions in the first detection stage and then perform image classification over these suggested regions. This saves all the manual effort required for determining parking regions for a given scene, making this approach more generalized for various parking scenarios. First, the parking region of interest is retrieved from the parking spot database. Then using its image coordinates a crop on a shared copy of the original input image frame is taken. This image crop then acts as an input to the classifier which provides real-time occupancy status prediction of the parking space.

D. Data Processing and Transmission

In the context of this paper, the application of this generated data is twofold; First, this acts as a database of available free and occupied parking spots; Secondly, this parking space could also be utilized to navigate misbehaving vehicles (in situations like wrong-way driving, distracted driving, etc.) to isolate them

from the rest of the traffic. But, to bridge the gap between the traffic surveillance systems and the vehicle driver, there is a need to efficiently send generated information to the vehicle in real time. To achieve this the generated parking data is further processed before its ready for data transmission.

To keep the data transmission volume to a minimum, we first calculate the centroid of each parking space in the database, therefore, reducing the number of associated data points. Then, we further calculate the GPS position of these centroids, by manually calculating homography between the traffic camera image and the geo-referenced satellite image of our test area, with 10 image points. This homography is then utilized to perform a perspective transformation of the traffic camera image to the satellite image. Respective GPS coordinates are then retrieved using the Python GDAL library. All the aforementioned processed data is then encapsulated in a JSON message which contains: a) Traffic camera details (id and GPS coordinates) and Parking Space Information (every space with its unique ids, GPS position, and their respective occupancy status).

For the data transmission, we utilize the high bandwidth network infrastructure provided by 5G META. As a part of this platform, we deployed our own Apache ActiveMQ message broker to enable data communication between the fog node in the municipality server and the 3D visualizer consumer application. The encapsulated JSON parking messages are then transmitted through this message broker using Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) as an application layer protocol enabling process-to-process communication across IP networks.

E. Visualizer

A 3D visualization for the implementation of an in-car HMI was developed using the Godot engine (version 3.2), which is

Fig. 2. The top view of the area in our visualizer. The highlighted red square represents the area in which we monitor the parking spaces in our sample setup.

a lightweight graphics engine that can be easily deployed on a wide variety of hardware platforms, including embedded and mobile boards. Godot is implemented in the C++ language and enables fine-tuning of many graphical aspects for our proposed smart-city application. Godot can be programmed using a specific scripting language for prototyping, however, it also supports the implementation of native C++ modules (GDNative), which is crucial for real-time HMI applications. Godot has been used in previous literature about HMI in the contexts of IoT, gamification and Extended Reality [23], [24]. After comparing Godot with other more popular alternatives (such as Unity and Unreal Engine), we opted to use Godot due to its gentle learning curve and easier porting to the NVIDIA Jetson family of embedded boards. The digital twin city scenario is extracted from OpenStreetMap (OSM), which allows us to retrieve a 3D mesh of the area in which we want to monitor the parking spaces. An aerial view of the area displayed within the visualizer, developed using the Godot engine, is shown in Figure. 2 which also highlights the trail site used for PSD experimentation, with a transparent red squared zone. Given the design of the entire PSD system, we chose not to implement a native C++ module for this visualization feature because the data arrives sporadically, with a delay of T_{sod} frames due to the time required for the PSD to classify static and moving vehicles. To receive the parking data into the 3D visualizer application, a consumer node is used which creates a queue with the ActiveMQ message broker exchange to receive the desired messages from the specific AMQP topic created by the producer. Once the connection from the 3D visualizer application is established with the exchange it can then start receiving the queued parking messages. These messages are then forwarded to the 3D HMI application through the UDP protocol, using the JSON format used by the entire system. Once the application receives the message, it is essential to re-project all the received GPS positions of the parking spots through a homography operation to translate them from GPS coordinates to the local (X, Z) coordinate system used in the 3D visualizer. To perform this operation, we calculate a homography matrix using three different pairs of $[GPS - (X, Z)]$ coordinates placed at the top left, top

Fig. 3. The visualizer notation on free and occupied parking slots. On the left, is a free parking spot. On the right, is an occupied parking spot.

right, and bottom right of the map respectively. Starting with the top left point, we can calculate the last point situated on the bottom left by Euclidean 2D calculation, and with these four couple of coordinates, we achieve a rectangular area. We then use these coordinates to auto-generate a large number of pairs inside the rectangular area and calculate the homography matrix. Let $GPS_{Latitude}$ and $GPS_{Longitude}$ be the latitude and longitude of a GPS coordinate, respectively, and let H be the 3×3 homography matrix. Let L and U be two 3×3 quadratic matrices, let k be a factor, and let X and Z be the final coordinates for the 3D visualizer (the results of the homography operation). The homography operation is defined by equations 1, 2 and 3.

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} GPS_{Latitude} & 0 & 0 \\ GPS_{Longitude} & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$U = D * H \quad k = \frac{1}{U_{1,2}} \quad L = U * k \quad (2)$$

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} X & U_{0,1} \cdot k & U_{0,2} \cdot k \\ Z & U_{1,1} \cdot k & U_{1,2} \cdot k \\ U_{2,0} \cdot k & U_{2,1} \cdot k & U_{2,2} \cdot k \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

As shown in the Equation 3 the local space position for the 3D environment, X and Z coordinates, are the $L_{0,0}$ and $L_{1,0}$ values respectively.

On the application side, for each parking spot detected and communicated by the infrastructure, we check if it already exists in the 3D visualizer. If the parking spot is new, we create a new entity and save it in a dictionary with the unique identifier (ID) of the parking spot as the key and the 3D object representing the parking spot in the 3D digital twin as the value. The chosen graphical look for the parking spots is shown in Figure 3. A placeholder with a P symbol indicates the presence of a parking spot, and a flattened hemisphere above the placeholder shows whether the spot is occupied or available for parking. We have depicted the parking spots with two states: *available* (or free) and *occupied*. To provide visual feedback and improve the *connection between the information and the users of the application*, we have developed a small loop animation for the hemisphere (an up and down animation)

and placed the word `free` above it when the parking spot is classified as free. When the availability of the parking spot changes from free to occupied, the animation is interrupted and the color of the hemisphere is set to a vibrant red. The opposite occurs when the availability changes from occupied to free.

IV. EVALUATION METRICS

In this section, we highlight the evaluation metrics used for our proposed architecture. Since the intention of this work is to propose a system architecture that can provide flexibility in choosing its individual system components (Object Detection and Tracking and Images Classification algorithms etc.), we conduct several experiments to investigate the following aspects: (i) how robust is the architecture to support different state-of-the-art algorithms for individual system components? (ii) System performance in real-world scenarios to support the proposed solution as a Smart-City application. (iii) Can the proposed architecture be easily generalized in a Smart-City context? In the following sections, we discuss the evaluation metrics used to achieve each aforementioned goal.

A. Evaluating architecture flexibility and robustness

With the intention of deploying the architecture in a real-world scenario, we choose different state-of-the-art pre-trained models to evaluate the performance of the proposed pipeline on fixed input data. For the Parking Detection stage, we evaluate the performance of the pipeline by testing five YOLOv5 pre-trained models. YOLOv5 repository from Ultralytics [18] provides a variety of pre-trained models on the MS-COCO dataset to choose from depending upon the trade-off between processing speed and the mAP (mean average precision) at 0.5:0.95 metric measured on the 5000 images of COCO val2017 dataset. Table I compares the performance of the five YOLOv5 models we use for testing our pipeline.

TABLE I
YOLOV5 PRE-TRAINED MODELS

Model	mAP val 50-95	Speed CPU ms	Speed GPU ms
YOLOv5n	28.0	45	6.3
YOLOv5s	37.4	98	6.4
YOLOv5m	45.4	224	8.3
YOLOv5l	49.0	430	10.1
YOLOv5x	50.7	766	12.1

^a Pixel size 640

Similarly, for the DeepSORT tracking algorithm, multiple ImageNet pre-trained models can be used from [25] depending upon the performance trade-off between the number of parameters and floating point operations. For simplicity in our experiments, we chose *osnet-x1-0* model which has over 2.2 million parameters and 0.98 GFLOPs. To evaluate the Static Object Detection (SOD) algorithm, we manually label the stationary vehicles by visual inspection from the pre-recorded video and then validate it through the outcome of the

proposed algorithm. SOD Detection Accuracy is the metric we use for evaluation, which is simply the ratio between the number of stationary vehicles detected by the SOD algorithm over the tracked vehicles by the Parking Detection stage through visual inspection. We record a video with 1392 frames from one of the cameras to perform this test. For the occupancy detection stage, we proposed to utilize space-based classification methods. To reduce the manual effort involved in labeling the parking spaces, in our implementation, we propose to use the bounding box regions from Static Object Detection results to select our region of interest for performing occupancy classification. To evaluate this strategy, we take the deep CNN classifier implementation from Amato et al. [12] which is a modified version of AlexNet called *mAlexNet*, designed to handle a binary classification problem. But, instead of manually labeling the parking spaces we test the accuracy of the classifier on the image crops we receive from the SOD stage which acts as a region proposal mechanism for parking spaces. For evaluating the classification accuracy, we create a dataset of SOD image crops from two different camera sources and further label it with their true values, to perform inference using the *mAlexNet* classifier.

B. System Performance Evaluation

To propose the suggested architecture as a Smart City application, it is essential to have low latency in terms of performance for each system component in the pipeline. To evaluate this, we measure the processing efficiency of individual components for a fixed given system input. For the object detection and tracking phase, we define the evaluation metric as the average processing time required per sampled frame. And for the rest of the system components (*Occupancy Classification, Data Processing, and Data Transmission*) we calculate the overall processing time required to perform each individual task. We further benchmark these performances with different YOLOv5 models.

V. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

Preliminary tests were performed in a lab setup with a pre-recorded video feed from the local municipality of the trial site. We recorded short video clips giving us around 1400 frames from different traffic cameras around the smart city trial site. The purpose of doing this was to test if the proposed solution can be easily generalized to a given camera within a city. The following tests were performed on 15 different cameras from our trial site but for the purposes of this paper, we present results from only one of these camera sources. To bring further diversity to our test conditions, we chose a camera facing toward the street, allowing us to test the roadside parking scenarios. Figure 4 shows the camera position selected for performing this test.

B. SOD Detection Accuracy

Static Object Detection accuracy results from a test conducted on the pre-recorded videos can be seen in Table II.

The classification task was performed after every 500 frames during the run-time and T_{sod} was set to 200 frames which is the threshold to categorize detected objects as static.

TABLE II
SOD ACCURACY RESULTS

Test Input	Actual Parking Spaces (Visual Inspection)	Detected Parking Spaces (SOD Results)	Detection Accuracy (%)
Video 1	13	12	92.30%
Video 2	14	13	92.85%

Maximum limit T_{sod} can be adjusted depending upon the input type. For example, here since the length of the video input was 1392 frames, the maximum limit T_{sod} was set on the lower end. Figure 4 are snapshots of the parking detection results and their respective SOD results on the two video sources respectively.

C. Occupancy Classification Accuracy

We created two data sets of 50 images each, from the image crops this stage receives as input from the parking detection and the SOD stages. The difference between the two data sets is that the first one contains occluded parking spaces and the second one has non-occluded spaces. Both these data sets have an equal number of occupied and vacant parking spaces.

Sample crop images from the data sets are shown in the rightmost column of Figure 4. We achieve overall accuracy of 90% on the first data set and 100% accuracy on the second data set. After comparing the results from these two data sets we can see that a drop in accuracy occurs in heavily occluded parking spaces, but the classification accuracy is higher in spaces that are in the clear perspective of the camera. Since our proposed architecture provides flexibility in choosing the classification algorithm, occlusion can be handled using other research methodologies used in space-based classification.

D. Processing Efficiency

To calculate the end-to-end processing efficiency of the proposed architecture, we perform tests in two different scenarios as mentioned in V-A. For simplicity, in this section, we present results only from one of these smart city cameras. We conducted the first test in a lab setup using a pre-recorded video and calculated the latency of each system component of the proposed architecture. Table V-D highlights the results of this test. The second test was performed on the live feed from the same camera on the fog node hosted in the server of local municipality authorities at the trial site. To keep the results comparable, we use the same parameter settings throughout the pipeline in both of these tests. In Table V-D we can see that the throughput of individual system components remains consistent in both the lab simulation environment and the real-world test thus highlighting the system architecture's benefits as a real-time smart city application.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

An end-to-end real-time smart-city application for parking space management was presented. A new system architecture was proposed and experimented with in a real-world setting to

justify it as an efficient smart-city application. By using vehicle detection and tracking algorithms to act as a region proposal mechanism for image classification, we eliminate manual efforts in hand labeling parking spaces. Implementing multi-threaded pipelines for detecting parking spaces and classifying their occupancy, allowed us to efficiently manage the available compute resources and scale up our application across multiple city cameras within our trial site in a short period of time. The proposed architecture also allows flexibility for selecting different algorithms for each stage of the pipeline without compromising overall performance, as demonstrated by the validation results. Furthermore, the proposed solution is also a financially viable option, as it does not incur additional hardware installation costs for parking space detection. On the user end of the architecture, a 3D visualizer application using a lightweight graphics engine was presented. The visualizer was able to present the location of parking spaces along with their occupancy status in real time with a higher degree of precision in the newly created digital twin of our trial site.

As a part of our future work, we plan to scale up this application across 30-plus cameras available currently on our trial site using the proposed architecture. Also, we would investigate further improving the overall parking occupancy classification accuracy on occluded parking spaces, which is currently 90% on our collected dataset. The 3D visualization application provides a broader range of customizable options to accommodate future developments within the PSD application. For example, information related to illegal parking scenarios could be used to signal the local authorities to conduct targeted checks in a given area. It would also be possible to implement a reservation mechanism for the parking spots. See a video of the system working at <https://youtu.be/t3umLVIMMwY>.

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Fig. 4. Parking space visualization from video source 1 & 2. Parking Detections (left) and Visualization Results (center). On the right we see sample crops of occupied space (top) and free space (bottom)

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE RESULTS

Platform GPU / Input source	Yolov5 Model	Latency (seconds)			
		Object Detection per frame	DeepSORT per frame	Classification & Data Processing	Data Transmission
NVIDIA TITAN RTX, (24220MiB) (pre-recorded videos)	yolov5n	0.039	0.026	0.014	0.087 (7cars)
	yolov5s	0.039	0.049	0.226	0.056 (16 cars)
	yolov5m	0.070	0.053	0.215	0.044 (16 cars)
	yolov5l	0.012	0.049	0.185	0.042 (16 cars)
	yolov5x	0.017	0.050	0.159	0.042 (16 cars)
NVIDIA TITAN V, (12066MiB) (Live video feed)	yolov5n	0.004	0.020	0.056	0.102 (7cars)
	yolov5s	0.004	0.026	0.071	0.342 (11 cars)
	yolov5m	0.007	0.030	0.098	0.097 (16 cars)
	yolov5l	0.010	0.027	0.103	0.079 (12 cars)
	yolov5x	0.017	0.031	0.123	0.106 (14 cars)

^a DeepSORT Model: osnet-ibn-x1-0; params: 2,194,640; flops: 978,878,352.

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